

Preliminary phytochemical study and medicinal aspects of *Cassia obtusifolia* L. (Ceasalpinaceae)

Dr. S. V. Deore

Department of Botany

J.E.S's, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Nandurbar-425412

Abstract

The current study is based on the phytochemical and medicinal aspects of *Cassia obtusifolia* L. a well known medical plant. Different plants parts of plant are taken under investigation for physical character study and qualitative and quantitative phytochemical estimation study. Presence or absence of a chemical i.e. qualitative analysis of drug will give the criteria to evaluate the drug or to standardize the drug. The present research work was confined to phytochemical study and medicinal value of *Cassia obtusifolia* L.

Keywords: *Phytochemical, qualitative, quantitative, medicinal plant and Cassia obtusifolia L.*

Introduction

Plants are most useful in human life. There is no human activity where the plants do not play a role. Ethnobotany in its widest sense has widest linkage with almost every other science and field of knowledge. As per Aiyeloja and Bello (2006) the traditional knowledge of indigenous communities about surroundings plant diversity and how various people make use of indigenous plants found in their localities (Chopra *et al.*, 1956). In current study we collected traditional knowledge about folk medicines used by local inhabitants about *Cassia obtusifolia* L. from Village folk especially the tribal people and analyzed collected sample in laboratory (Dastur 1962 and Jain S. P., Varma D. M. 1981).

In Maharashtra *Cassia obtusifolia* L. is a widely distributed plant on road and path side, this having various important medicinal value, belonging to the family Ceasalpinaceae. *It* used for skin diseases, like ringworm and itch (Ugemuge, 1986, Igoli *et al.*, 2005), leaves are antipyretic diuretic, anthelmintic and laxative, asthma, bronchitis, fruit and seeds are anthelmintic, to cure tumors (Kumar

and Bhattacharjee, 1998), antimicrobial activity (Kumar and Bhattchaejee, 1998 and Putnam, *et. al.*, 1988). Plant used in Ayurvedic medicine and Unani system of medicine. A warm poultice of leaf is a good remedy in gout, sciatica and pain in joints (Maheshwary, 2000). Plants are antifungal, leaf laxative used in skin diseases, sciatica, leprosy, gout, pain in joints, snake bites (Jayvir Anjaria, *et. al.*, 2002). Emodin is isolated from *C. obtusifolia* seed that's shows larvicidal activity against mosquito species (Young *et. al.*, 2003 and Jaing *et al.*, 2007). The natural antifungal plants extract were collected from *Cassia obtusifolia* (Brij Bhushan *et. al.*, 2006).

Materials and Methods

The samples were collected from local forest area and road sides from Nandurbar taluka areas and identification were done with the help of Flora of Dhule and Nandurbar District by Dr D. A. Patil in Department of Botany. Different plants parts like roots, stems and leaves were separated carefully by hand pricking without damaging the plants and put them into shade dry in laboratory. After drying grinding the material of like roots, stems and leaves by making fine powder had been made separately for each. These powder have been using for phytochemical analysis with standard methods.

Physical parameter like Colour, Odour and Taste has been studied for root, stem and leaf of *Cassia obtusifolia*. Chemical parameter like qualitative and quantitative aspects tested for each part of plant (Drever *et al.*, 2008 and Rajasekaran Narmadha and Kanakasabati Devala, 2012).

Result and Discussion

A) Physical parameters:

- i) **Colour:** The root, stem and leaf powders of selected plants species root, stem and leaf drugs have following colours. *Cassia obtusifolia*, root – faint brown, stem – brown, leaf – dark green. *Cassia tora* root – whitish brown, stem – brown, leaf – dark green (Table 1).
- ii) **Odour** *Cassia obtusifolia* root –characteristic, stem – characteristic, leaf – pungent. *Cassia tora* root – characteristic, stem – characteristic, leaf – pungent (Table 1).
- iii) **Taste:** *Cassia obtusifolia* root – tasteless, stem – slightly sweet, leaf – slightly sweet. *Cassia tora* root – tasteless, stem – slightly sweet, leaf – sweet (Table 1).

Sr. No	Plant Parts	Colour	Odour	Taste
1	Root	Faint brown	Characteristic	Tasteless
2	Stem	Brown	Characteristic	Slightly sweet
3	Leaves	Dark green	Pungent	Slightly sweet

B) Chemical parameter:

i) **Qualitative parameters:** Alkaloids are present in investigation. Almost all the alkaloids have one or other Medicinal property and hence their presence in the medicinal plants. The major natural chemical groups such as steroids, reducing sugar, saponin, alkaloids, phenolic compound, amino acid, tannins etc are present as per table 2 (Rajasekaran Narmadha and Kanakasabati Devala, 2012). The Anthraquinone test showed its presence in *Cassia obtusifolia* stem, Analysis of iridoid test reveals presence of iridoid in leaves. Saponins, Tannins and Steroids were reported in stem (Table 2).

Sr. No	Plant Parts	Alkaloids	Anthraquinone	Iridoids	Saponins	Steroids	Tannins
1	Root	+	-	-	+++	+	-
2	Stem	+	+	+	+	+	++
3	Leaves	+	-	-	++	+	+++

ii) **Quantitative parameters:** - Dry matter (DM), Bulk density, Total Ash (TA), Acid insoluble ash (AIA), Acid soluble ash (ASA), Water insoluble ash (WIA), Water soluble ash (WSA), Nitrogen (N), Water soluble nitrogen (WSN), Crude protein (CP), Reducing sugars, Non-reducing sugars, Total sugars, Crude fats (C fat), Crude fibers (CF), Cellulose, Gross energy (GE), Calcium (Ca), Phosphorus (P) and Extractive values in Water, Diethyl Ether, Ethyl alcohol, Acetone, Butanol, Chloroform, Methanol, Petroleum ether and Propanol. These quantitative character and presence for *Cassia obtusifolia* root, leaf and stem as per in table 3.

Table 3. Chemical parameter for quantitative aspects of *Cassia obtusifolia*

Sr. No	Plant Parts	D.M.%	B.D.in mg/cm ³	Total Ash	insoluble ash Acid ash	Acid soluble insoluble ash	Water ash	Water soluble ash	Nitrogen	protein	Crude
1	Root	59.19	0.425	04.80	1.85	04.00	04.80	1.0	2.30	22.01	
2	Stem	35.85	0.392	09.41	1.21	08.41	05.41	2.0	3.01	17.02	
3	Leaves	51.01	0.438	11.33	3.05	09.49	08.29	3.0	3.51	13.56	

Conclusion

Three main important parameters of *Cassia obtusifolia* L. has been studies with respect to root, stem and leaves extracts in different solvents. It was found that plants has significant therapeutic importance and hence effective in most of folk medicinal practices. Some parameters are present in one parts were other shows negative results , it may due to the plant parts difference or may be due to solvent type in extraction procedure. Mainly all parts of plants shows presence of alkaloids in all parts are important factors in therapeutic activity. Collective the plant having well sources of medicinal valve and also used by many tribes in their different medicinal purpose further needs to more estimation at molecular level to reveals active compound from plant.

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